

DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN-THE FOUNDATION OF THE NEW RENAISSANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8036629>

Annotation. This article argues that in the updated Uzbekistan, the development of the educational sphere is considered at the level of state policy, primarily comprehensive support for young people seeking to master modern science. It is necessary to note the current territory of Uzbekistan went down in history as an ancient cradle of science, culture and art and the first Renaissance period in the IX-XII centuries and the second Renaissance period in the XIV-XVI centuries as the habitat of great scientists and thinkers who made a great contribution to the development of world science. It should be noted that the spirit and blood of our great ancestors still exist in our youth, and therefore they will become the founder of the third Renaissance.

Keywords: development of education, preschool education, secondary education, higher education, development of science, first Renaissance, second Renaissance, third Renaissance.

Introduction Modern life cannot be imagined today without the progress of Science, Science and education. It is also not for nothing that the development of Science and education in the leading countries of the world is defined as a master task. It is in this direction that the future prosperity of the country is closely related to its achievements. The development of Science and education is one of the important steps towards the main force, prosperity and stability that leads any state, including the new Uzbekistan, to development.

Therefore, in the updated Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the radical reform of the system of Science and education and to bring to adulthood the perfect generation, worthy successors of our tomorrow, to be formed as worthy descendants of our great-grandchildren. In the following years, laws, decrees, state programs related to the field of Science and education are adopted and educational institutions based on modern science are being established. At the same time, a new generation of teachers and mentors who are engaged in education are receiving material and moral support. "Today we are laying the foundation for the new development period of Uzbekistan. Our closest assistants in this are teachers and mentors, scientific and creative intellectuals" ["Халқ сўзи" газетаси. 09. 10. 2020]

In our country, special attention is paid to the field of science, enlightenment, education, especially the value of intellectual wealth is directly related to the history, spirituality, mentality, centuries-old values, aspirations of our people. The Central Asian region, in particular the territory of today's Uzbekistan, has been recognized in World Science as one of the ancient cradles of science, culture and art in history, and for the next thousand years Two Renaissance eras have come here.

Today Uzbekistan aims to create a new Renaissance-the foundation of the third Renaissance-through science, educational reforms. This means that a high level of development of national statehood, market economy and democratic society is being achieved through science and education reform.

Literature analysis methodology

Based on the analysis of the literature studied, it should be noted that according to the mutahasis who conducted studies (Gurol Irzik, Keegan, Lewis and Jameson Murphy, Andre Louie, Pappas Christopher, Duffin Erin, McCue TJ lar, B from Russian scientists.S. Ryabushkin, A.A. Bakulina O.V. Loseva I.V. Raeva K.E. Kalinkina et al.) modern science and education are fundamentally different in all respects from the science and education that existed a century or even half a century ago. Therefore, the content of today's science and education has significantly, significantly changed the nature of their relationship with society. If we focus on the levels of development of science, then in modern society science renders the organic unity of three basic concepts: science as knowledge, science as activity, science as a social institution. It is known that science has a centuries-old tradition of knowledge (A.V.Starsev, Z.R.Tanaeva, V.K.Terziev, G.B.Chiladze, E.L.Shilkina, S.M. S.V.Shoshin) a special form of social consciousness, representing a specific system of knowledge as a product of the educational system. Such a direction of science makes conclusions only by relying on reliable, proven evidence, knowledge. Therefore, the possibilities of deeper and comprehensive study of its social nature, creators, specifics, structure, place, social role and functions of science are limited. This led to the need to study the role and social aspects of Science in the educational system.

The manifestation of science as an activity makes humanity a significantly productive force of the scale and pace of modern scientific and technical progress. (I.S. Baklanov, M.B. Sinelnikov, O.A. Baklanova, A.I.Zelenkov, L.A.Zelenov, V.V.Zuev, V.I.Kashpersky, V.P.Kokhanovsky et al. This jaroyon was first recorded in the middle of the last century, in the way of a human activity-based approach to science, as a result of which science began to be interpreted as a special area of professionally specialized activity, a product of Education, a kind of spiritual production.

Science as a social institution - a special socio-professional group, based on the educational system, is the unity of organizing the activities of scientists who are a certain community. (N.V. Basov, L.A. Verbiskoy. D.Bell, 3.Bell, D.M.Castels, A.V.Chugunov, V.V.Vasilkovoy, L.A.Verbiskoy, N.Shter, N.N.Semenov, B.S.Ryabushkin et al.) also, as a social institution, the purpose of science is to produce and disseminate scientific knowledge through education, to develop research tools and methods, to ensure that scientists increase and fulfill their social functions.

The issues of science, enlightenment, education, their incomparable contribution to World Science are perfectly expressed in the works of Central Asian thinkers. Their invaluable services are deeply analyzed in the works of local and world-renowned scientists. (I.Mo 'minov, A.Kubesov, M.Dinorshoev, M.Khairullaev, Z.Kuli-Zada, V.Bartold et al.) these scholars have researched the scientific treasure of thinkers and the heritage of masterpieces on the basis of historicism, dialectical techniques.

The research methodology has effectively used the methods of analysis and synthesis, analytical analysis, comparative analysis during scientific research. In our study, a deeper study of the problem was carried out through the directions of comparative analysis,

analytical analysis. Strategic directions leading to the solution of the problem are defined. As an object of research, science and educational institutions, educational processes are covered.

Discussion

A special place in the development of each state is occupied by the system of Science and education. The establishment of an excellent and effective education system based on science was considered important for all countries in each period.

It is known that the Central Asian region, in particular, the territory of today's Uzbekistan, as an ancient cradle of science, culture and art in history, was the cradle of the first Eastern Renaissance or Muslim renaissance in the 9th-12th centuries, the second renaissance in the 14th-16th centuries-the land of ulugalloma and thinkers, who greatly

It should be noted that the Central Asian region, in particular the territory of today's Uzbekistan, has also been mentioned in pre-Islamic sources in history as a land with advanced ideas in the field of civilization and education of science. In particular, the "Avesto" put forward progressive ideas for its time in relation to the spiritual environment, science and education. For the fact that the territories of Uzbekistan are historically located at the intersection of the Great Silk Road and its various branches, people wishing to receive religious and secular knowledge from different countries of the East and the world have always sought out large cultural centers such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorezm, Nasaf (Karshi), Kesh (Shahrisabz), Tashkent, Fergana. In these areas, the madrasas, a place of knowledge that operated from ancient times, were in the status of a higher educational institution of their time, that is, Universities.

According to all Eastern and Western scholars, the first Renaissance in Europe, which occurred between the 15th and 17th centuries, took place in our country a few hundred years earlier, that is, in the 9th and 11th centuries. There are their own historical reasons for the occurrence of this huge rise, of course. Because during this period, new reforms and laws were introduced that were very important for the development of the state, radical updates took place from land-water, neighborly relations to taxes. Innovations in state administration and Politics United the people of Science in the world of noble ideas, interest in various sciences, especially mathematics, astronomy, chemistry, medicine, law, Geodesy, and modern theories about the structure of the world were founded precisely at that time. In addition to being great ancestors such as Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Rayhan Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Ahmad al-Farghani Abu Nasr Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hojib, Mahmud Koshgari, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Imam Bukhari, Imam Termiziy, Imam Moturudi, Abul Muin Nasafi, our great ancestors attained the status of mentoring all over the world in their subjects.

The Second Renaissance is closely associated with the name of our great-grandfather, Sahibqiron Amir Temur, who carried out political-economic and social reforms not only in our region, but also in very large geographical areas. Thanks to him, a state based on powerful Central Management and a favorable situation for a new cultural and scientific rise arose. ushered in the Second Renaissance. During this period, classical poets and thinkers such as Rumi, Mirzo Ulugbek, Ghiyosiddin Koshiy, Ali Qushchi, benazir scholars, Lutfiy, Sakkokiy, Hafiz Khwarazmiy, Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Babur Mirzo took to the square. The fame of such historians as Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Mirkhand, Khondamir, musicians like Mahmud Muzahhib, Kamoliddin Behzod, many calligraphers and musicians, musicologists and

architects spread around the world. As in the first Renaissance, in this period, those wishing to learn science began to flow from all over the world.

This is based on information published in the fundamental work "the Muslim renaissance" by the Austrian-born Orientalist Adam Mes in 1909 [2.str3-7, 211-267, 397-473.] From then on, views and studies began to be published that the Renaissance was not an exclusively European phenomenon, which Eastern peoples experienced earlier in relation to Europeans. [4. Russia I ATR, 2013, №1, S. 133-141.]

Russian great Orientalist academic N. N. According to Conrad [5. Str.3-10, 103-204, 455-496] that the Renaissance began in China in the 7th — 8th centuries and continued in India in the 8th century, from which the Islamic countries adopted the relay in the 9th-12th centuries, the rise, which had fallen considerably due to the Mongol invasion, re-gurkurab grew again under Amir Temur and the Timurids. It extends the Middle Eastern Renaissance to the time of Alisher Navoi. Jawoharlal Nehru had also judged Babur to be a typical representative of the Renaissance.

Today, the followers of the exalted and thinkers of our country are forming. Head of State Sh. Mirziyoev noted that "in the present time, when the glorious power of our people is fizzled, a new renaissance – the third Renaissance-is being laid in Uzbekistan, so to speak, the same will be true" [6. "Халқ сўзи" 1.10.2020]

Result

Science, education — is the main force leading any state to development. Therefore, for Uzbekistan, the development of Science and education is one of the important steps towards prosperity and stability. Public policy in the field of development of Science in our country is based on the system of continuing education. That is, education begins in kindergarten and continues in the school, higher education, doctoral and later stages.

Engaging in science leads to new discoveries and inventions being made. This is due to the fact that the question of the New Renaissance - the third Renaissance, which Uzbekistan has chosen, is being raised to the level of a national idea as a strategic task.

As the president noted, the funds used for the development of fundamental Sciences will give results not one day. We are laying the foundation for the third Renaissance. When the necessary conditions are created in schools, there is no husband in the world as hardworking and patient as an Uzbek child in obtaining knowledge. The Renaissance will be anyway. As long as we have put before ourselves the exaltation of building the foundation of the third renaissance in our country, for this we must create environments and conditions that will educate the new khwarazmians, Berunians, ibn Sina, Ulugbek, Nawab and Babur.

... Why do we spend so much on mathematics, chemistry, biology? Tomorrow these fundamental sciences will show the result anyway. After all, it was once so" [WWW "Gazeta uz". 29 08.2020]

Presidential decisions and decrees being adopted in this direction remain the legal basis for the formation of the third Renaissance generations. Over the past period, more than 100 regulatory legal acts aimed at the development of these areas, including the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on science and scientific activities", "on preschool education and education", "on education"and hakoza, are serving the development of such areas.

Therefore, in the country, comprehensive measures have been developed for the further development of the field of education and science. It provides for a number of issues such as improving the quality of Education, building new school buildings, reconstruction,

overhaul, full provision of them with modern educational and laboratory equipment, information and communication technologies and educational and methodological manuals through the implementation of broad reforms in the system of public education and higher education. Particular attention is paid to the in-depth teaching of a number of subjects, including foreign languages, mathematics, physics, Informatics, chemistry, biology, in a radical improvement in the quality of general secondary education.

The establishment of talented children's schools named after Mirzo Ulugbek and Muhammad Khwarazmiy, Hamid Olimjon and Zulfiya, Erkin Vohidov, Abdulla Oripov, Ibroyim Yusupov, Iskhaqkhan ibrat, Muhammad Yusuf, Khalima Khudoyberdieva, creative schools named after Mirzo Ulugbek and Muhammad Khwarazmiy, educational institutions of a new and modern pattern, as well as private schools, opened up new opportunities for the children of our country giving.

As the main pillars of the third renaissance in our country, kindergarten educators, school teachers, professors and scientific staff of higher education institutions will be a vivid example of the progress of science, economy and society, all the achievements that are carried out with the noble intention of serving the people and pleasing people-menimz and our youth-the strength of mental intelligence, talent and talent.

Suggestions and recommendations

First of all, with the introduction of the program "Modern School" on the Republic, it is necessary to bring the formation, development, application of subjects in practice into the educational system using simple, interesting concepts. For example, special courses such as "interesting history", "interesting chemistry", "interesting mathematics" and hakoza should be given the way to create the first discoveries of yoshar.

Secondly, the goal is to further expand the cooperation of educational institutions with foreign educational institutions, to establish a systematic way of training not only professor teachers of higher education, but also students and school teachers in schools in developed countries along with prestigious educational institutions.

Thirdly, it is necessary to carry out joint scientific and practical projects of educational institutions together with major foreign science centers, leading science institutions, to provide financial support to the government system and provide benefits to entrepreneurs providing practical assistance to educational institutions in this direction and to expand the scope of these works.

Fourth, at least one or more schools should be established in the areas of mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology, history, jurisprudence or other sciences in the province, which created all the conditions taking into account the scientific potential of the territory, the presence of high-ranking officials.

Implementation of the above, in the words of our president, the "Golden fund" of Uzbekistan will be formed. As a result, the khwarazmians, Berunians, ibn Sina, Ulughbek will be the basis for the emergence from among our youth, and the foundation for the foundation of the literally New Renaissance in Uzbekistan will be laid.

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